

SUB GROUP	ELEMENT NAME	ELEMENT DESCRIPTION / UNITS
1. Informed consent and Biobank	Consent for the processing of the pseudoanonymised data within the project	I confirm that patient consent has been obtained which allows the processing of this pseudoanonymised clinical information within this project
	Consent for re-use of pseudonymized data by third parties	I confirm that patient consent has been obtained for re-using of pseudonymised data by third parties in order to contribute to projects whose objectives are directly connected to improve healthcare provision for rare hematological disorders
	Consent for transfer of pseudonymized data to non-EU countries	I confirm that patient consent has been obtained for transferring pseudonymized data to non-EU countries in order to contribute to projects whose objectives are directly connected to improve healthcare provision for rare hematological disorders
	Consent for being re-contacted	I confirm that patient consent has been obtained for being re-contacted by his/her medical doctor in order to be informed about potential participation in a research project and/or clinical trial related to their condition
	Participant's data is already in a db	Is patient data already stored in a database
	Biological sample research	Is patient biological sample available for research?
	Biological sample in Biobank	Is the patient biological sample stored in a biobank?
	Biobank link	Could you provide the patient biobank website link?
2. Patient Status	Date of birth	Patient's date of birth
	Sex	Patient's sex at birth
	Patient status	Patient alive or dead
	Date of death	Patient's date of death
	Main cause of death	What was the main cause of death?
	Visit Date	Date of physical examination
	Length/ Height	Patient's length/ height (cm)
	Weight	Patient weight (kg)
	Diastolic blood pressure	mmHg
	Systolic blood pressure	mmHg
	Heart rate	/min
	Oxygen saturation rate	Measured by pulse oximetry (%)
	Comorbidities	Does the patient have any relevant comorbidity?
	Comorbidities (specify)	Specify which comorbidities does the patient have
3. Patients' care pathway	Country of living	Patient's country of residence
	City of living	Patient's city of residence
	Country of birth	Patient's country of birth
	Year of immigration	Year of immigration
	Mothers' country of birth	Patient's mother country of birth
	Fathers' country of birth	Patient's father country of birth
	Healthcare Provider ID	Name of the Healthcare Provider (HCP)
	Physician ID	Name of the physician in charge of the patient In the current ...
	First contact with specialised centre	Date of first contact with specialised centre

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4. Diagnosis	Clinical course of disease	What was the clinical course of the disease?
	Method of diagnosis (Select all that apply)	Specify the method on which the diagnosis is based
	(Clinical/Medical) Diagnosis date	Date / Time period of clinical diagnosis
	(Clinical/Medical) Diagnosis - specify date	Date of clinical diagnosis
	(Clinical/Medical) Diagnosis age	Age at clinical diagnosis
	(Clinical/Medical) Diagnosis	Diagnosis retained by the specialised centre
	(Clinical/Medical) Subdiagnosis	Sub-diagnosis
	Genetic diagnosis date	Date of genetic diagnosis
	Gene	ID of gene
	Allele 1	Genetic diagnosis retained by the specialised centre
	Allele 2	Genetic diagnosis retained by the specialised centre
	Date / Time period at onset	Date / Time period at which symptoms/signs first appeared
	Age at onset	Age at which symptoms/signs first appeared
	Reason for diagnosis	Reasons for the diagnosis of the patient
	First symptoms	First symptoms shown

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5. Chronic organ damage	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Liver MRI	Liver Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (msec)
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Liver MRI (Date)	Liver magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) Date
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Liver SQUID Date	Liver SQUID Date
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Liver Squid	Liver SQUID (mg/g dry weight)
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Fibroscan Date	Fibroscan Date
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Fibroscan Result	Fibroscan (kPa)
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Liver biopsy	Liver biopsy (mg/g dry weight)
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Liver biopsy date	Liver biopsy date
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Cardiac Iron T2	Cardiac iron T2* (ms)
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Cardiac Iron T2 Date	Cardiac iron T2* Date
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Cerebral MRI	Was Cerebral Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) performed in the last 12m ?
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Transcranial Doppler	Transcranial Doppler
	Chronic organ damage assesment in the last 12 months: Conditional or abnormal TCD	Conditional or abnormal TCD
	Chronic complications of bones and extremities	Information on chronic complications of bones and extremities
	Chronic cardiac and pulmonary disease	Information on chronic cardiac and pulmonary disease
	Chronic neurological disease	Information on chronic neurological disease
	Chronic endocrinologic disease	Information on chronic endocrinologic disease
Chronic liver and kidney disease	Information on chronic liver and kidney disease	
6. Organ damage	Visual and hearing diseases	Information on visual and hearing diseases
	Acute complications requiring hospitalization or emergency admission for more than 24 hours (SCD)	Has the patient affected by SCD had hospitalizations or Emergency admissions for acute events?
	Acute complications requiring hospitalization or emergency admission for more than 24 hours- Date (SCD)	Hospitalization/Emergency Admission Date, for SCD patients
	Main acute complication requiring hospitalization or emergency admission for more than 24 hours (SCD)	Main reason for each Hospitalization/Emergency admission for SCD patients
	Secondary acute complications requiring hospitalization or emergency admission for more than 24 hours (SCD)	Secondary reason(s) for each Hospitalization/Emergency admission for SCD patients
	Acute complications requiring hospitalization or emergency admission for more than 24 hours- Mechanical ventilation (Main reason)	Did the patient require mechanical ventilation ? (Main reason)
	Acute complications requiring hospitalization or emergency admission for more than 24 hours- Mechanical ventilation (Seondary reason)	Did the patient require mechanical ventilation ? (Secondary reason)
	Intensive Care Unit Admission	Has the patient had any Intensive Care Unit (ICU) admission

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8. Spleen	Splenomegaly	Does the patient have splenomegaly on physical examination?
	Splenectomy	Has the spleen been removed?
	Date of splenectomy	Date of spleen removal
	Reason for splenectomy	Why was the spleen removed?
9. Cholelithiasis	Cholelithiasis	Does the patient have cholelithiasis?
	Cholecystectomy	Did the patient have cholecystectomy?
	Cholecystectomy Date	Date of cholecystectomy
	Cholecystectomy reason	Reason for cholecystectomy
10. Disability	Patient's disability profile according to International Classification of Functioning and Disability (ICF)	Does the patient have Disability?
	Patient's disability profile according to International Classification of Functioning and Disability (ICF)-Score	Score
	Patient's disability profile according to International Classification of Functioning and Disability (ICF)-Profile	Profile
11. Offspring	Fertility	Is the patient infertile?
	Offspring	Has the patient had offspring? (fathered a child for males / been pregnant for females)
	Chronic complications of bones and extremities	Information on chronic complications of bones and extremities
	Chronic cardiac and pulmonary disease	Information on chronic cardiac and pulmonary disease
	Chronic neurological disease	Information on chronic neurological disease
	Chronic endocrinologic disease	Information on chronic endocrinologic disease
	Chronic liver and kidney disease	Information on chronic liver and kidney disease

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12. Blood transfusion	Transfusion status in the past	Did the patient require regular or occasional transfusions in the past (all patient's history)?
	Transfusion status in the present	Does the patient require regular or occasional transfusions in the present (in the last 12 months)?
	Transfusion status in the past	Reasons for stopping regular transfusion
	Transfusion status in the present	Type of regular transfusion
	Date of first regular transfusion	Date of first regular transfusion
	Indication for regular transfusion	Indication for regular transfusion
	Year	The year for which transfusion data is provided
	Goal Hb pre-transfusion	Goal for Hb concentration pre-transfusion Measured in g/L
	Number of transfusions	If transfusions are regular, number of transfusion events in the past 12 months
	Transfusion interval	52 weeks/number of transfusion (automatically retrieved)
	mL/ transfusion event	Amount of mL per each transfusion event
	Blood consumption	Calculation of blood consumption per year (mL/Kg/year) (automatically retrieved)
	Adverse event	Any type of adverse event related to the transfusion
	Main causes (triggers)	Main causes of Occasional Transfusion
13. Chelation	Chelation	Is the patient on chelation treatment?
	Drug	Specific drug multiple chelators
	Date	Year of beginning chelation treatment
	Dose used for chelation	Daily dosage in mgs
	Dose per Kg	mgs / Kg
14. Hydroxyurea	Hydroxyurea	Is the patient on hydroxyurea treatment (present time)?
	Hydroxyurea in the past	Has the patient ever been on hydroxyurea?
	Date	Start date of hydroxyurea treatment
	Cumulative years on treatment with Hydroxyurea	Cumulative years on treatment with Hydroxyurea
	Dose used	Daily dosage in mgs
	Dose per Kg	mgs / Kg
15. Specific treatment and/or inclusion in research protocols	Specific treatment	Is the patient currently on an specific treatment?
	Ongoing treatment	Specific treatment ongoing for the disease
	Patient involved in a Clinical Trial protocol	Is the patient involved in a Clinical Trial protocol?
	Patient involved in a Clinical Trial protocol: Clinical Trial ID	Clinical Trial ID
16. Haematopoietic stem cell transplantation (HSCT) / gene therapy	HSCT transplant/gene therapy	Has the patient been transplanted/received gene therapy?
	HSCT transplant/gene therapy: Date	Date of HSCT/gene therapy transplant
	HSCT transplant/gene therapy: Type	Type of HSCT/Gene therapy transplant
	HSCT transplant/gene therapy: Outcome	HSCT/gene therapy outcome
	HSCT transplant: reason	Reason for not being transplanted

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17. Laboratory test	Red blood cell (RBC) number	$10^6/\text{mm}^3 - 10^{12}/\text{L}$
	Hemoglobin (Hb)	g/dL
	Mean corpuscular volume (MCV)	fL
	Hematocrit (HCT)	%
	Mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH)	pg
	Mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC)	g/dL
	Red cell distribution width (RDW)	%
	Reticulocytes count (absolute) - reference	$10^3/\text{mm}^3$
	Reticulocytes count (absolute)	$10^{12}/\text{L}$
	Reticulocytes count (%)	/1000 RBC - %
	White blood cell (WBC) count	$10^3/\text{mm}^3 - 10^9/\text{L}$
	Platelet count	$10^3/\text{mm}^3 - 10^9/\text{L}$
	Hemoglobin F	%
	Hemoglobin F in diagnosis	%
	Abnormal Hemoglobin Fraction	Is there any abnormal Hemoglobin fraction?
	Abnormal Hemoglobin Fraction - Specify	%
	Serum iron	$\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$
	Ferritin serum	ng/mL - $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$
	Transferrin	mg/dL
	Transferrin saturation %	%
	Transferrin receptor	mg/L
	Alanine transaminase (ALT)	U/L
	Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH)	U/L
	Total bilirubin	mg/dL
	Unconjugated bilirubin	mg/dL
	Conjugated bilirubin	mg/dL
	Haptoglobin	mg/dL
	Creatinine	mg/dL
	Glomerular filtration	mL/min/1.73m ²
	Blood film morphology	Result for the test
	Hyperchromic red blood cell (RBC)	%
	Hypochromic red blood cell (RBC)	%
	Erythroblasts fraction	%
	Erythroblasts absolut	$10^9/\text{L}$
	Neutrophils	$10^9/\text{L}$
	Lymphocytes	$10^9/\text{L}$
Monocytes	$10^9/\text{L}$	
Eosinophils	$10^9/\text{L}$	
Basophils	$10^9/\text{L}$	
MPV platelet	fL	

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17. Laboratory test	Glucose (not fasting)	mg/dL
	Total iron binding capacity	mcg/dL µmol/L
	Serum Folic acid	ng/mL
	Urea	mg/dL
	Sodium	mmol/L
	Potassium	mmol/L
	Calcium	mg/dL
	25-(OH) D	ng/mL
	Parathyroid hormone (PTH)	pg/mL
	Cholesterol	mg/dL
	Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol	mg/dL
	High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol	mg/dL
	Triglycerids	mg/dL
	Aspartat aminotransferase (AST) serum	UI/L
	Alkaline phosphatase (ALP)	UI/L
	Gamma glutamyl transferase (GGT)	UI/L
	C-Reactive protein (CRP)	mg/dL
	Procalcitonin (PCT)	ng/mL
	Proteins (serum)	g/dL
	Albumin	g/dL
	Creatinuria (urine)	mg/dL
	Proteinuria (urine)	mg/dL
	Proteinuria / Creatinine (urine)	mg/g creatinine
	Albuminuria (urine)	mg/dL
	Abuminuria / Creatinuria (urine)	mg/g creatinine
Renal impairment grade	Automatically generated according to KDIGO classification.	

HMDB_CODE	HMDB_NAME	RELEVANCE	ORIGIN	FLUIDS
HMDB00002	"1,3-Diaminopropane"	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00005	2-Ketobutyric acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00008	2-Hydroxybutyric acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00010	2-Methoxyestrone	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00012	Deoxyuridine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00014	Deoxycytidine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00015	Cortexolone	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00016	Deoxycorticosterone	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Amniotic Fluid; Blood
HMDB00017	4-Pyridoxic acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00019	Alpha-ketoisovaleric acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00020	p-Hydroxyphenylacetic acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Food; Microbial	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Saliva; Urine
HMDB00021	Iodotyrosine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood
HMDB00022	3-Methoxytyramine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00026	Ureidopropionic acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00027	Tetrahydrobiopterin	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF)
HMDB00030	Biotin	Endogenous, relevant	; Food	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00031	Androsterone	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00032	7-Dehydrocholesterol	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00033	Carnosine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00034	Adenine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00036	Taurocholic acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Bile; Blood; Urine
HMDB00037	Aldosterone	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Saliva; Urine
HMDB00038	Dihydrobiopterin	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF)
HMDB00039	Butyric acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food; Microbial	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Saliva; Urine
HMDB00043	Betaine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00044	Ascorbic acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Drug ; Food	; Amniotic Fluid; Blood; Cellular Cytoplasm; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00045	Adenosine monophosphate	Endogenous, relevant	; Drug metabolite; Endogenous	; Blood; Cellular Cytoplasm; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00048	Melibiose	Endogenous, relevant	; Microbial	; Urine
HMDB00050	Adenosine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cellular Cytoplasm; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00052	Argininosuccinic acid	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Urine
HMDB00053	Androstenedione	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous; Food	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00054	Bilirubin	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Bile; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine
HMDB00056	Beta-Alanine	Endogenous, relevant	; Endogenous	; Blood; Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF); Urine